

Differences and Relationships in the Academic Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation of Students

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Abstract

As motivation plays a significant role in one's completion of certain task in general, so as motivation is essential to students in performing academic tasks in particular. This study aimed to further the investigations about the academic intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of students. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions: 1) what is the reliability of the inventory as used in this study?; 2) are there significant relationships between the overall intrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between the intrinsic motivation factors?; 3) is there a significant difference among the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors?; 4) are there significant relationships between the overall extrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between one extrinsic motivation factor and every other extrinsic motivation factor?; 5) is there a significant difference among the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors?; 6) is there a significant relationship between the overall intrinsic and overall extrinsic motivation of students?; and 7) is there a significant difference between the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of students? This study adopted the proposed Academic Intrinsic Motivation Questionnaire of Regina Shia in her study, entitle "Assessing Academic Intrinsic Motivation: A Look at Student". The inventory is made up of six factors. Two are considered intrinsic motivation factors, namely: mastery goals and the need for achievement. While, four are considered extrinsic motivation factors, namely: authority expectations (family and professor), peer acceptance, power motivations, and fear of failure. A sample of 120 was taken from the students of the Bachelor of Science in Cruise Management at John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. enrolled during the first semester of academic year 2014-2015. Non-proportionate stratified random sampling method, stratified according to year level and sex, was employed in this study. This study revealed the following: 1) the obtained Cronbach's alpha was 0.923 (0.926 based on standardized items), 2) significant relationship exists but no significant difference was found among the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors, 3) significant relationship exists and significant difference was found among the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors, and 4) significant relationship exists and significant difference was found between the overall intrinsic and overall extrinsic motivation of the students. The inventory was found to possess a high level of consistency. On one hand, the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors are directly related among each other and they are of the same value. On the other hand, the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors are directly related among each other, but they are of different values. There are factors found to be higher than some. Furthermore, direct relationship was found between the overall intrinsic and overall extrinsic motivation of students but they are of different values. The overall intrinsic motivation of students is higher than their overall extrinsic motivation; hence, students are intrinsically motivated rather than extrinsically motivated.

Keywords: motivation, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, academic motivation

Introduction

According to Pintrich and Schunck (as cited in Grabu, 2009), “motivation is the process whereby goal-directed activity is initiated and sustained.” It is probably the most important factor that educators can target for the enhancement of learning (Williams & Williams, n.d.). Hence, a number of works about academic motivation were done.

Among the works on academic motivation was the study of Regina Shia, entitled “Assessing Academic Intrinsic Motivation: A Look at Student”. In her study, she proposed an inventory that is made of six factors: two are intrinsic factors and four are extrinsic factors. Intrinsic motivation factors include the mastery goals and need for achievement. According to Dev (as cited in Shia, n.d.), intrinsic motivation is defined as a) participation in an activity purely out of curiosity for there is a need to know about something, b) the desire to engage in an activity purely for the sake of participating in and completing a task, and c) the desire to contribute. On the other hand, the extrinsic motivation factors include the authority expectations (family and professor), peer acceptance, power motivations, and fear of failure. According to Hoyenga and Hoyenga (as cited in Shia, n.d.) extrinsic motivation refers to motives that are outside of and separate from the behaviors they cause; the motive for the behavior is not inherent in or essential to the behavior itself.

This study was conducted to further the investigation of the abovementioned author using her proposed inventory.

Statement of the Problems and Hypotheses

This study aimed to determine the differences and relationships in the academic intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of students. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

- 1) What is the reliability of the inventory as used in this study?
- 2) Are there significant relationships between the overall intrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between the intrinsic motivation factors?
- 3) Is there a significant difference among the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors?
- 4) Are there significant relationships between the overall extrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between one extrinsic motivation factor and every other extrinsic motivation factor?
- 5) Is there a significant difference among the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors?
- 6) Is there a significant relationship between the overall intrinsic and overall extrinsic motivation of students?
- 7) Is there a significant difference between the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of students?

In line with the problems, the following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

- 1) There are no significant relationships between the overall intrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between the intrinsic motivation factors?
- 2) There is no significant difference among the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors?
- 3) There are no significant relationships between the overall extrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between one extrinsic motivation factor and every other extrinsic motivation factor?
- 4) There is no significant difference among the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors?
- 5) There is no significant relationship between the overall intrinsic and overall extrinsic motivation of students?
- 6) There is no significant difference between the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of students?

Significance of the Study

This study may be beneficial to teachers, students, and researchers.

Teachers may take into consideration the use of the inventory to know the dominant type of motivation of his or her students. Preparation of learning activities may be guided by the prevailing type of motivation of the students.

Students may increase their self-awareness specifically on what drives them to perform well in the class. They may use the inventory to confirm their dominating type of motivation.

Other researchers in the field of academic motivations may utilize the results of this study in their future research endeavors.

Delimitation of the Study

The respondents in this study were taken from the Bachelor of Science in Cruise Ship Management students of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. enrolled during the first semester of academic year 2014-2015. The data used in this study were collected during the said semester.

Although the sampling technique employed in this study was non-proportionate stratified random, stratified according to year level and sex, this does not dwell on the relationships and differences with those student-related factors.

Cronbach's alpha was used to establish the reliability of the instruments with the chosen sample. Although mean and standard deviation were introduced, this study focused on inferential

analysis using the nonparametric tests, namely: Friedman test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and Spearman's rank-order correlation.

Methodology

This study made use of the quantitative-descriptive research design.

Respondents of the Study

The sample in this study was 120 students from the Bachelor of Science in Cruise Ship Management (BSCSM) of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo) enrolled during the first semester of academic year 2014-2015. Non-proportionate stratified random sampling method, stratified according to year level and sex, was employed in this investigation. Using the developed computer program, 15 male and 15 female students were randomly selected from first year to fourth year.

Instrumentation

This study adopted the inventory proposed by Regina Shia in her study, entitled "Assessing Academic Intrinsic Motivation: A Look at Student". The inventory is composed of 60 statements measuring the two intrinsic motivation factors: mastery goals and need for achievement; and four extrinsic motivation factors: authority expectations (family and professor), peer acceptance, power motivations, and fear of failure. Ten statements, which are numbered 3, 6, 7, 8, 12, 27, 29, 31, 49, and 51, measure the mastery goals. Ten statements, which are numbered 1, 22, 23, 25, 26, 28, 33, 34, 48, and 60, measure the need for achievement. Nine statements, which are numbered 13, 20, 32, 36, 44, 45, 47, 50, and 59, measure the authority expectations. Eleven statements, which are numbered 5, 9, 10, 24, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, and 58, measure the peer acceptance. Ten statements, which are numbered 11, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 21, 30, and 46, measure the power motivation. While, ten statements numbered 2, 4, 35, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, and 43, measure the fear of failure.

Each statement is rated on a 7-point Likert scale (1=does not describe me; 7=absolutely describes me). The rating to each statement is the corresponding weight, except to the 18 statements numbered 8, 9, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20, 22, 33, 36, 37, 40, 43, 44, 46, 55, 56, and 58, which are stated in opposite, hence the corresponding weight for each statement is the reverse.

Data Analysis

Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the reliability of the inventory based on the responses of the students in the sample.

Spearman's rank-order correlation was used to determine the relationships between the overall intrinsic motivation and its every factor, between the intrinsic motivation factors, between the overall extrinsic motivation and its every factor, between one extrinsic motivation

factor and every other extrinsic motivation factor, and between the overall intrinsic motivation and overall extrinsic motivation.

Friedman test was used to determine the difference in the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors, and overall extrinsic motivation and its factors.

Wilcoxon signed-rank test served as post hoc test to determine the specific differences in the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors. Also, this was used to determine the difference between the overall intrinsic motivation and overall extrinsic motivation.

Mean and standard deviation were used to present descriptive statistics.

Results and Discussion

Reliability of the Inventory

Performing the reliability test on the Academic Intrinsic Motivation Questionnaire using the data from the respondents, the obtained Cronbach's alpha value was 0.923 (0.926 based on standardized items).

Relationships in the Intrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

Utilizing the Spearman's rank-order correlation, strong and direct relationships were found between the overall intrinsic motivation and its every factor, and between the two factors: mastery goals and need for achievement.

Table 1 shows the obtained Spearman's correlation coefficients describing the relationships.

Table 1

Relationships among the Overall Intrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

	Overall Intrinsic	Mastery Goals	Need for Achievement
		$r_s (p)$	$r_s (p)$
Overall Intrinsic		.896* (0.000)	.903* (0.000)
Mastery Goals			.637* (0.000)
Need for Achievement			

* $p < 0.05$

Difference in the Intrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

Utilizing the Friedman test, no significant difference was found in the intrinsic motivation and its factors, $\chi^2(2)=2.483, p=0.289$.

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors. It may be observed that the computed mean values are close to each other.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of the Overall Intrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

	<i>M (SD)</i>
Overall Intrinsic	5.39 (0.776)
Mastery Goals	5.40 (0.854)
Need for Achievement	5.37 (0.812)

Relationships in the Extrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

Utilizing the Spearman’s rank-order correlation, strong and direct relationships were found between the overall extrinsic motivation and its every factor, namely: authority expectations, peer acceptance, power motivations, and fear of failure. Also, strong and direct relationships were found between authority expectations and peer acceptance, authority expectations and fear of failure, peer acceptance and power motivations, peer acceptance and fear of failure, and power motivations and fear of failure. While, moderate and direct relationship was found between authority expectations and power motivations.

Table 3 shows the obtained Spearman’s correlation coefficients describing the relationships.

Table 3

Relationships among the Extrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

	Overall Extrinsic	Authority Expectations	Peer Acceptance	Power Motivations	Fear of Failure
		<i>r_s (p)</i>	<i>r_s (p)</i>	<i>r_s (p)</i>	<i>r_s (p)</i>
Overall Extrinsic		.743* (0.000)	.796* (0.000)	.800* (0.000)	.864* (0.000)
Authority Expectations			.517* (0.000)	.452* (0.000)	.565* (0.000)
Peer Acceptance				.550* (0.000)	.587* (0.000)
Power Motivations					.615* (0.000)
Fear of Failure					

* $p < 0.05$

Difference in the Extrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

Utilizing the Friedman test, a significant difference was found in the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors, $\chi^2(4)=16.306, p=0.003$. Post hoc analysis with Wilcoxon signed-rank tests was conducted with a Bonferroni correction applied, resulting in a significance level set at $p < 0.005$. Significant differences were found between the overall extrinsic motivation and authority expectations ($Z=-2.845, p=0.004$), overall extrinsic motivation and power motivations ($Z=-3.226, p=0.001$), and authority expectations and power motivations ($Z=-3.368, p=0.001$). While, no significant differences were found between the overall extrinsic motivation and peer acceptance ($Z=-0.039, p=0.969$), overall extrinsic motivation and fear of failure ($Z=-0.767,$

$p=0.443$), authority expectations and peer acceptance ($Z=-1.992, p=0.046$), authority expectations and fear of failure ($Z=-1.134, p=0.257$), peer acceptance and power motivations ($Z=-2.001, p=0.044$), peer acceptance and fear of failure ($Z=-0.263, p=0.792$), and power motivations and fear of failure ($Z=-2.790, p=0.005$). The mean value corresponding to the authority expectations is greater than either the overall extrinsic motivation or power motivations; while, the mean value corresponding to the overall extrinsic motivation is greater than power motivations.

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics and the results obtained from conducting the post hoc analysis to determine the difference in the learning preferences describe in the BLSI.

Table 4

Descriptive Statistics and Difference in the Overall Extrinsic Motivation and Its Factors

	<i>M (SD)</i>	Overall Extrinsic <i>Z (p)</i>	Authority Expectations <i>Z (p)</i>	Peer Acceptance <i>Z (p)</i>	Power Motivations <i>Z (p)</i>	Fear of Failure <i>Z (p)</i>
Overall	4.89		-2.845 ^a	-0.039 ^a	-3.226 ^b	-0.767 ^a
Extrinsic	(0.742)		(0.004)	(0.969)	(0.001)	(0.443)
Authority Expectations	5.03			-1.992 ^b	-3.368 ^b	-1.134 ^b
	(0.840)			(0.046)	(0.001)	(0.257)
Peer Acceptance	4.87				-2.001 ^a	-0.263 ^a
	(0.878)				(0.044)	(0.792)
Power Motivations	4.74					-2.790 ^a
	(0.884)					(0.005)
Fear of Failure	4.93					
	(0.984)					

a. Based on positive ranks

b. Based on negative ranks

Relationship between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

Utilizing the Spearman’s rank-order correlation, strong and direct relationship was found between the overall intrinsic motivation and overall extrinsic motivation.

Table 5 shows the obtained Spearman’s correlation coefficients describing the relationship.

Table 5

Relationship between the Overall Intrinsic and Overall Extrinsic Motivation

	Overall Intrinsic Motivation	Overall Extrinsic Motivation $r_s (p)$
Overall Intrinsic Motivation		.645* (0.000)
Overall Extrinsic Motivation		

* $p < 0.05$

Difference between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

Utilizing the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a significant difference was found between the overall intrinsic motivation and overall extrinsic motivation, $Z=7.445$, $p=0.000$. The mean value corresponding to the overall intrinsic motivation is greater than the overall extrinsic motivation.

Table 6 shows the descriptive statistics and the results obtained from computing the difference between the overall intrinsic motivation and overall extrinsic motivation.

Table 6

Descriptive Statistics and Difference between the Overall Intrinsic and Overall Extrinsic Motivation

	<i>M (SD)</i>	Overall Intrinsic	Overall Extrinsic <i>Z (p)</i>
Overall Intrinsic	5.39 (0.776)		-7.445 ^a (0.000)
Overall Extrinsic	4.89 (0.742)		

a. Based on positive ranks

Conclusions

The proposed Academic Intrinsic Motivation Questionnaire possesses high measures of internal consistency. The statements reliably measure the same variable. Hence, inventory reliably measures the proposed construct.

The overall intrinsic motivation and its factors directly correlate to each other. As one factor increases, the other also increases; hence, its overall intrinsic motivation also increases. In addition, there is no significant difference in the overall intrinsic motivation and its factors. The difference in the computed means was attributed to sampling error. Therefore, the overall intrinsic motivation and the intrinsic motivation of students as to mastery goals and need for achievement are the same.

Although there are variations as to the degree of relationship, but the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors: authority expectations, peer acceptance, power motivations, and fear of failure, directly correlate to each other. As one factor increases, the other also increases; hence, its overall extrinsic motivation also increases. However, there is a significant difference in the overall extrinsic motivation and its factors. The authority expectations factor is higher than either the overall extrinsic motivation or power motivations factor. Further, the overall extrinsic motivation is higher than the power motivation factor. Therefore, external motivation factors of students are not the same. This seems to imply that between authority expectations factor and power motivations factor, the former is considered by the students more; hence, it may influence them at a greater extent.

The overall intrinsic motivation and overall extrinsic motivation directly correlate to each other. Hence, as the intrinsic motivation gets higher, the extrinsic motivation also gets higher, and vice versa. However, there is a significant difference between them. The overall intrinsic motivation is not the same as the overall extrinsic motivation; the former is higher. Therefore, this group of students has higher intrinsic motivation than extrinsic motivation. Results, however seem to imply that both motivations influence the students; only that internal motivations influence them at a greater extent.

Recommendations

Teachers may use the inventory to measure the academic intrinsic and extrinsic motivation of their students. This, in some way, may help them prepare learning activities to their students.

Students may try answering the inventory for self-awareness. Their knowledge about their motivations might help them change some of their preferences should they find external motivation to be not so ideal.

Researchers may conduct similar studies involving other variables. Further studies are encouraged to confirm or refute the results of this study and augment information on this area.

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Academic Intrinsic Motivation Inventory by Regina M. Shia

	Does not describe me				Absolutely describes me		
1. I want to learn everything I need to learn.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2. Finishing an exam first leaves me afraid that I did something wrong or forgot something.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3. No matter how much I like or dislike a class, I still try to learn from it.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4. When faced with a difficult test, I expect to fail before I expect to do well.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5. I sign up for the same classes that my friends sign up for.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6. I feel that challenging assignments can be great learning experiences.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7. College helps me to gain valuable knowledge.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8. My quality of performance is dependent on my grade in the class.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9. Academics are the last thing that I want to talk about when hanging out with my friends.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10. When I receive a low grade on an exam, I try to hide it from others.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11. I feel good about myself when others do not understand material that is clear to me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12. I learn simply for the sake of learning.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13. When I have to make an academic choice, I go to my parents for advice.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14. I prefer difficult tasks as opposed to moderate tasks.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15. I never boast about my grades.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16. I am not one of the smartest students in my class.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17. I am satisfied with an average grade, as long as I learn from my mistakes.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18. I sign up to take the easiest teacher so that my grades will be better.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19. I feel helpless about school after receiving a few bad grades.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20. I have no preference to impress "power figures".	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
21. Finishing an exam quickly makes me feel good.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22. I work best in a group environment.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23. I do all that I can to make my assignments turn out perfectly.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24. I feel more accepted by others when I receive a good grade on a test.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25. I sign up for the classes that will prepare me for the future.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
26. I have high expectations of myself.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
27. I see myself as well-informed in many academic areas.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
28. I get frustrated when I find out that I did not need to study as much as I did for a test.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
29. Sometimes I do more than I have to for an assignment to help me understand the material better.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
30. I find my ability to be higher than most of my peers.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

	Does not describe me				Absolutely describes me		
31. I enjoy learning about various subjects.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
32. Being in college gives me the opportunity to prove to my family that I can achieve something.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
33. I wait till the last minute to complete my assignments.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
34. I would only sign up for a club if it helped me to reach a long-term goal.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
35. I feel ashamed when I receive a low grade.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
36. I have no problem telling my parents when I receive a bad grade on an exam.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
37. I feel that my ability is sufficient in the classroom.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
38. Even when I have studied for hours, I don't feel that I have studied enough.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
39. I get nervous when my professor begins to hand back tests.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
40. I enjoy challenging tasks.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
41. I get frightened that I will not remember anything when I take a test.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
42. In my studies, I set short term, goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
43. I have no doubts that I will achieve my academic goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
44. My academic interests are not influenced by anyone but myself.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
45. It is important to complete assignments the way that my professor would want them completed.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
46. It does not bother me when others perform better than I on a test.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
47. When I do poorly on an exam, I feel that I let my professor down.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
48. I feel good about myself when I finish a difficult project.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
49. I like to spend time reading about things that interest me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50. I try to live up to what my professor expects out of me in the classroom.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
51. I try to do my best on every assignment.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
52. I like to be one of the most recognized students in the classroom.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
53. I sign up for the same classes that my friends sign up for.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
54. I have the same attitude toward college as my friends.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
55. I study best when I am alone.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
56. I still want to go to class even when my friends don't go.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
57. I feel that the smarter I am, the more accepted I will be by other students.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
58. My grade point average is nowhere near the grade point average as my friends.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
59. I feel that I should be recognized when I demonstrate my abilities in the classroom.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
60. I set high goals for myself.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7